

THE TRIBAL WAY OF BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION THROUGH THE OBSERVANCE OF RELIGIOUS RITUALS - A CASE STUDY IN SELECTED SANTAL VILLAGES OF MANBAZAR – 1 BLOCK, PURULIA DISTRICT, WEST BENGAL

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Abstract : Conservation of biodiversity has become essential in the present-day with concerning to sustainable development. The role of indigenous tribes in traditionally conserving the biosphere is undeniable. The religious beliefs, taboos, traits, rituals and customs of the Santal community are directly related to the preservation of various plants and animals because they worship various plants, animals and nature as gods and goddesses. Religiously, one of the holy places of this tribe is *Jaherthans* (sacred groves); all kinds of their religious ceremonies, festivals, rituals etc. are started by performing worship at *Jaherthans*. These are the reason they protect these holy places as possible as they can do. Another most important side of these sacred grooves is that these are the habitats of a wide variety of plant and animal species, meaning that they act as local biodiversity hotspots, which play a vital role in conserving local biodiversity.

Keywords: Religious beliefs, *Jaherthans* (Sacred grooves), Biodiversity, Santal tribes.

Introduction

Religious places, traditional beliefs, customs, cultural traits and practices play a vital role in the conservation of biodiversity. In rural India, many plants and animals are considered religiously sacred, as they have absorbed cultural values among tribal communities. Religious belief serves as a protective tool for these rare forest species (Pandey, 2003). Plants and trees have a greater importance in the life of the tribes not only for economic purposes, but also from the point of view of their social and cultural importance to preserve the ancient tradition of the tribal peoples of the area. Various trees and plants are of religious and health importance throughout tribal India. When it comes to preserving them, tribal peoples are more willing to save biological resources than anything else, since their survival and life activities depend directly on them (Sing, 2017). For the protection and conservation of biodiversity, tribal culture is full of different knowledge systems, rules and traditional rituals. In different places, different deities are believed to live on different sacred plants. Due to obtaining food and drinks from some plants in times of crisis, people also consider such plants as

sacred. Some plants are also considered sacred by people for certain reasons, such as medicinal usefulness, the living place of the souls of their ancestors, etc. In all circumstances and obstructions, they continue to do everything possible for the protection and conservation of these sacred plants. The clan, lineage and *gotra* of different tribal communities, are named in the name of different animals as a cultural taboo, they never killed such animals (Nayak, 2016).

The approach of the Santals towards environment is environment-centric and they bear a deep-rooted, age-old relationship with the nature. The conservation of the environment is an integral part of the cultural and religious ethics of the Santal tribes, especially in rural areas. In the context of religious practices, the sacred groves (SGs) are the main religious place where Santal people worship nature, i.e. plants, animals, rivers, mountains, etc. (Chakraborty, 2019). The SGs are locally known as *Jaherthan* and the idols of *Jaherthan* are namely *Marang Buru* (Lord Siva), *Jaher Era* (Goddess Durga), *Gosae Era* (The lady spirit who takes care of the other spirits at the *Jaherthan* and safe the villagers and never does any harm), *Pargana Bonga* (A spirit who protects a geographical entity), *Majhi Bonga* (A spirit who protects the village), *Sima Bonga* (A village boundary spirit) and *Moreko-Turuiko* (Ancestors of the villagers). Religious observances and SGs are intimately related to each other in Santal society because all cultural and religious festivals, rituals, traits, etc. are organized primarily at the SGs. The SGs are believed to be a treasure house of medicinal and aromatic plants (Kandari et. al, 2014). One of the significant roles of this religious place and religious traits is to conserve natural resources which are dedicated to the god or goddess or ancestral spirits. (Jain, 1998) The SGs culture maintains ecological balance and also helps in the conservation of biodiversity and also helps in following aspects such as: 1) soil conservation, 2) continuous creation of water cycles, 3) increasing groundwater table, 4) natural pollination, 5) naturally seed conservation and creation of new plants, 6) Protection and conservation of regional plants and animals, 7) carbon sequestration, 8) temperature control, and 10) conservation of traditional knowledge etc.

(Malhotra et. al, 2001). Therefore, they are of central importance with regard to ecological conservation and forest management and conservation policy at the state and national level (Singh et. al 2017).

For the present study, ten sample villages have been taken under Manbazar-1 block of Purulia district in the state of West Bengal. The reason behind the selection of these villages are (i) the villages are dominated by Santal tribes, and (ii) Villagers, still they follow the traditional way of life i.e. follow their religious beliefs, customs, rituals etc. -The main objectives of the study are to depict the religious importance of the sacred groves in the Santal tribal society and to illustrate the relation between religious beliefs (sacred totems) and biodiversity conservation. The detail of the Study area is shown in the table 1 and figure 1.

Table 1: Absolute location of the studied villages

Sl. No.	Name of the villages	Coordinates	
		Latitude	Longitude
1	Bagsarka	23°03'30.7"N	86°43'22.1"E
2	Bongara	23°03'46.8"N	86°43'14.4"E
3	Gotgora (Bankati)	23°03'40.9"N	86°44'02.2"E
4	Jaisinghpur	23°04'23.8"N	86°43'09.5"E
5	Dulalpur	23°04'36.6"N	86°43'33.0"E
6	Dhabani	23°04'24.4"N	86°43'59.7"E
7	Kalabani	23°04'33.6"N	86°42'20.1"E
8	Panisgora	23°04'02.3"N	86°44'23.2"E
9	Sriramghutu	23°05'19.3"N	86°44'15.0"E
10	Bagaldhara	23°05'04.6"N	86°44'42.1"E

Fig. 1: Location map of the study area

Materials and Methods

The present study is based on both primary and secondary data. To collect the primary data a field survey was conducted in these villages in October 2019. Information

associated with sacred groves, deities and totems, communities’ perception on flora and fauna, ethnomedicinal importance of various plants and it’s relation with taboos and approaches’ regarding different tangible and non-tangle resources has been collected through Schedule. To extract the information about individual phenomenal experiences and knowledge about their environs as well as their culture, personal interviews were also conducted at different times in October to December 2019 among aged people (>55). Secondary data were collected through various books, research articles, reports etc. on Santals’ society & culture as well as environment & ecology.

Results and Discussion

• **Religious importance of sacred grooves among Santals**

The villagers of the study area especially aged people stated that the community celebrates various religious festivals throughout the years and all the festivals are associated with *Jaherthan*. All the religious, as well as socio-cultural rituals that are observed throughout the year are basically started by worshipping various deities in *Jaherthan*. Therefore, *Jaherthan* is deeply involved in the religious practices of the Santals. These year-round religious ceremonies, on the other hand, play a significant role in maintaining the material balance as well as the conservation of biodiversity. The following is a description of the relationship of nature with the religious ceremonies, rituals and festivals observed at different times of the year.

Sohrae is celebrated in the month of *Pous* (December-January). It is also called the harvest festival. Pigs, goats, fowls and eggs are offered by the village *naeke* (village priest) in the *Jaherthan*.

Baha is celebrated in the month of *Phagun* (February-March). The first fruits of *matkom* (*bassialatifolia*) and other wild fruits and flowers, mainly the *sarjom* (*Shorea robusta*) flower are being offered. The *Naeke* and the *Kudam Naeke* (assistant priest) offer sacrifices of fowls at the sacred grove in honour of *Maram Buru*, *Jaher Era* and *Moreko- Turuiko*.

ErokSim is celebrated in the month of *Asar* (June-July). Sowing of rice seeds in the field. The *naeke* sacrifices the fowls to the *Jaher Bongas* (the god and goddesses or spirits of *Jaherthan*) and the *Manjhi Bonga*, invoking each one of them to make the earth fertile.

HariarSim is celebrated in the month of *Srabon* (July-August). It is the time when the paddy seeds start sprouting. The *naeke* sacrifices fowls to the village *Bongas* (sprits or god and goddesses of the villages), namely *Maran Buru*, *Jaher Era*, *Gosae Era*, *Moreko-Turuiko*, *Pargana Bonga*, *Majhi Bonga* and *Sirma Bonga* for luxuriant growth of paddy.

Iri-Gundli is celebrated in the month of *Bhador* (Sept-Oct). The first fruits of the *milletiri* (*panicum millaceum*) and *gundli* (*panicum frumentaceum*) are offered to the *Bongas*. The *Kudam Naeke* along with the fruits of the millet offers sacrifices of goat or ram to the *Pargana Bonga* to protect their crops from rats or other pestilences. *Janthar* is celebrated in the month of *Anghar* (Nov-Dec). The first fruits of the winter rice crop offering. The *Kudam Naeke* offers the sacrifice of goat or ram to the *Pargana Bonga* along with the first ears of paddy to protect from stomach disease, to multiply the paddy and also protect their gains from harm.

Magh Sim is celebrated in the month of *Magh* (Jan-Feb) when the *sauri* (thatching grass) is being cut. Fowls are sacrificed by the *Naeke* to the village *Bongas*, invoking them to multiply their *sauri* crop.

• **Relationship between religious beliefs and biodiversity conservation.**

The santal tribe protects SGs from degradation or distortion because of their religious beliefs. Not only previously mentioned festivals but also different rituals like marriage rituals, after-birth rituals, after-death rituals etc. have a religious relation with SGs. According to the

villagers, the *Karam* festival is not only celebrated after the end of paddy cultivation but if a *karam* (*Mitragyna parvifolia*) tree grows or is seen in someone's house or within the village boundary, and then the tree is worshipped as *Karam Banga*. This is usually the reason why the inhabitants of this area, as well as Santal tribes, conserve this plant.

Another important factor that also plays a vital role in the conservation of the biosphere is the totems of the clans of the Santal tribes. Each clan of the Santal tribes' follows a certain totem with which it helps directly or indirectly to conserve the biosphere. Because of these taboos or beliefs, no. flora and fauna are worshipped by them or all considered to be spirits. They do not consume or use these floras and fauna but protect and preserve them. There are twelve clans among the Santal, namely Hansda, Murmu, Kisku, Hembrom, Marandi / Mandi, Soren, Tudu, Baske, Besra, Chonre and Pauria, and each of them has different types of sacred totems. The clan-based totems and protected flora and fauna are mentioned in the following table.

Table 2: Clan-based totems and protected flora and fauna

Clans	Protected flora and fauna
Murmu	<i>Magnolia</i> flower (<i>Magnolia grandiflora</i>), <i>Kurchi</i> flower (<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i>), <i>Palash</i> leaf and flower (<i>Buteamonosperma</i>), Nilgai (<i>Boselaphus tragocamelus</i>).
Hansda	Mushroom (<i>Agaricus bisporus</i>), Duck (<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>)
Kisku	Screw pine flower (<i>Pandanus</i>), Vulture (<i>Aegypius Monachus</i>), Horse (<i>Equus caballus</i>), Squirrel (<i>Sciuridae</i>).
Hembram	<i>Amlaki</i> (<i>Emblicmyrobalan</i>), Vulture (<i>Aegypius Monachus</i>), Silkworm (<i>Bombyx mori</i>), Conch (<i>Strombus</i>).
Soren	<i>Amlaki</i> (<i>Emblicmyrobalan</i>), Silkworm (<i>Bombyx mori</i>).
Mandi	<i>Pial</i> tree (<i>Buchanania lanzan</i>), Horse (<i>Equus caballus</i>), <i>Palash</i> leaf and flower (<i>Buteamonosperma</i>).
Baske	Squirrel (<i>Sciuridae</i>), Vulture (<i>Aegypius Monachus</i>).
Besra	Crow (<i>Corvus</i>), Hawk (<i>Buteo jamaicensis</i>).
Chonre	Vulture (<i>Aegypius Monachus</i>), Lizards (<i>Lacertilia</i>)
Pauria	Squirrel (<i>Sciuridae</i>), Pigeon (<i>Columbidae</i>).

Besides these, some plants are also considered sacred by the santal people because of their medical utility. These medicinal plants always play a very important role in their life. Different types of ethnomedicinal plants have been found in these village surroundings, which are basically conserved for their utility. The following table showing the various ethnomedicinal plants and their uses-

Table 3: Medicinal plants protected and used by the Santal villagers

Santal name	Scientific name	Part used	Diseases
Kawet	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Leaf	Sprain
Kalmegh	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> Nees	Leaf	Boil
Taledare	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L.	Tomentum of leaf	External cut
		Root	Seminal weakness

		Gum	Jaundice
Murut	<i>Buteamonosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	Flower	White discharge
		Seed	Intestinal worm
Raher dare	<i>Cajanuscajan</i> (L.) Millsp.	Leaf	Jaundice
Shasang dare	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Rhizome	Boil
		Rhizome	Sprain
Dhutra	<i>Daturametel</i> L.	Leaf	Boil
		Root	Knee arthritis
Karajdare	<i>Millettiapinnata</i> (L.) Panigrahi	Seed	Boil
		Seed	Heel crack
		Seed	Itching
Rangoni	<i>Solanum surattense</i> Burm.f.	Seed	Malaria
		Seed	Toothache
Kodedare	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Stembark	Stomachache, gastric problem
Sengal sing	<i>Tragia involucrate</i> L.	Seed	Hair fall
		Root	Scorpion sting

The religious beliefs of these Santal people living in the lap of nature have always been associated with *Jaherthans* and these *Jaherthans* have been playing a significant role in conserving the biodiversity of the local area for many decades. But over time, their socio-cultural and economic life began to change, refine and expand. Rural-urban migration occurred for various reasons such as occupational reasons, educational attainment, as well as the betterment of life and the lifestyle, become transformed because of cultural assimilation with other communities. However, the biggest problem in the conservation of biodiversity at present is that with the increase in the rate of education among the young generation, they are reluctant to follow the Religious rules, as a result of which the SGs are becoming neglected and the biodiversity is also declining. In addition, with the advancement of modern medicine, there is no interest in preserving medicinal plants among the Santals, which is having a negative impact on the conservation of the biosphere. However, the vigilant vision of the government can accelerate the conservation of biodiversity in the midst of preserving the culture of these tribes.

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